
A Study of Quality of Life of Working Professionals during COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT: The recent COVID-19 Pandemic has created havoc in the order of the world in terms of health care, well being as well as economy. India has also been affected adversely by this pandemic. The adverse effects are evident in health of the people; their well being is negatively affected because of this deadly virus. Apart from the health aspect, the lockdown that happened as a precautionary measure in time of the pandemic affected the economy of the nation in a negative way. The GDP of our country has dropped significantly lower which is most adversely affecting the working professionals of our country. Due to the sinking economy employment instability has increased manifold. People have either lost their jobs or are very apprehensive about the fact that they might lose their jobs in future. The currently working professionals are also not being paid full salaries; their salary is either cut to some amount or is reduced to half. These uncertainties in jobs are affecting people's financial condition. Already people are physically affected by corona conditions and psychologically also there is a lot of apprehension regarding the corona virus conditions and when will the situations be normal. All these aspects are affecting the quality of life of working professionals. Quality of life as defined by WHO is the individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals. The quality of life of an individual is mainly assessed in terms of physical aspect, psychological aspect, social relationships and environmental aspect. These aspects, in light of the covid situation's impact on working professionals, are discussed in detail further in the paper.

KEYWORDS: covid-19, well being, quality of life

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INTRODUCTION

The current situation around the globe, with COVID-19 pandemic at its surge, sinking economies and people being affected by this physically, mentally and financially, paints a dire picture of the crisis that we are all facing today. COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by the novel corona virus. It is an infectious disease that causes respiratory diseases to animals and humans. Corona virus encompasses some similar types of diseases like Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). COVID-19 was discovered in the year 2019 and the first case recorded was in a Chinese city, Wuhan. This disease gets transferred from one person to another easily because as an infected person sneezes or coughs the saliva droplets get

dispersed in the surrounding and thereby infect the things nearby. Hence as soon as any other person comes in contact with those infected things they also carry the virus with them and eventually get infected either by touching their nose, mouth or eyes. This disease primarily affects the respiratory system of the infected person who has low immunity and since there are no vaccines or cure for this, covid-19 becomes very fatal. Due to its infectious and contagious nature COVID-19 was declared as a global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO). As of now more than 43 million confirmed corona cases have been found globally (World Health Organization, 2020). The conditions in India is also bad because cases are still rising with more than 7 million affected people currently in India (World Health

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Organization, 2020) but due to timely lockdown the death rate in India is not very high as compared to other parts of the world. In India as a precautionary measure for the corona virus initially a 21 day complete lockdown was announced on March 24, 2020. Later the lockdown was extended with some relaxation to access places which were of primary need. Though the lockdown was a precautionary measure and it did control the situations in India but this took an adverse toll on the economy of the country.

Due the lockdown for a prolonged period it significantly reduced the gross domestic product of economies around the globe. Hence our economy is no exception to this. The lockdown which continued for almost a period of 3-4 months led to the decrease in the production of various goods and services. Many people lost their jobs or in other cases the salaries remained pending. This resulted in the reduced purchasing power of the people in our country. The economy saw a huge downfall in the last two quarters of the current financial year (1st April 2020-31st March 2021). The growth rate for our economy has reduced so much that it is lowest after the recorded growth rate of 1.1% in the year 1991-92. This pandemic affected many major sectors of the economy such as telecom sector, aviation and tourism sector, automobile sector and many more. This period of no economic activity worsened the condition of the economy. The downward trend was common for both consumption and expenditure. Commodity wise the major set-back was felt by the non-essential good market. As there existed less or negligible income generation during the period of lockdown hence people spending was majorly focused on the essential goods only. If the sector wise study is done on the present scenario of our economy then we can say that the contribution is most from the consumer and retail business sector that is 18% of the total gross domestic product of our country. It is then followed by food and agriculture sector, transportation and logistics and then aviation and tourism. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) declared the expected Gross Domestic Product growth rate for India as 1.9% during the financial year 2021-2022. This growth is highest among all the G-20 nations in the world. This pandemic is yet not completely over hence deducing any facts in advance would only produce ambiguous results.

The employment sector of our economy is the worst stricken by the pandemic and the nation-wide lockdown. Majority of employees either lost their jobs, got their salaries reduced or worked without being paid through work from home channel. The new normal for the working professionals is work from home in which they are struggling to strike a balance between the work-life and personal-life. It was found that majority of employers were finding it difficult to maintain the existing human resource in the organizations. This led to the severe actions such as employee downsizing, layoff or retrenchment. This affected all the working professionals especially people working in the corporate sector. These major decisions were similar for both organized and unorganized sector of our

employment sector. Just in one month from mid-march to mid-april the unemployment percentage in our economy increased from 6.7% to 26%. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) estimates that this pandemic outbreak resulted in the loss of 40 crore jobs in India alone and more than 200 crore job loss globally. In India the work culture is very diverse and vast due to the large number of population in our country. This period of lockdown created an upsetting scenario of job and even food insecurity among many working professionals. The sudden announcement of nationwide lockdown brought down many income earning job opportunities among people. The migrant workers, small scale industries workers and other employees working even in huge multi-national companies faced the wrath of uneven income and even joblessness. The people engaged in the Micro Small and Medium Enterprise Industry faced a huge challenge in paying back the loans and advances taken in the hope of better returns this year. Although the Government has intervened in order to improvise this degrading situation of unemployment or job loss. Government on both national and state level has taken various steps to help either the employers or the employees that have suffered due the lockdown.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), quality of life is defined as “the individual’s perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals.” Quality of life (QOL) is the overall well-being of an individual and the societies, identifying negative and positive aspects of life. It consists of the expectations of a good life for an individual and society in an overall spectrum of well being. These expectations are influenced by the values, goals of an individual. Socio-cultural aspects also play major role in individual’s expectations of quality life. It serves as a reference against which an individual or society can measure the different aspects of his personal life. Extent to which one’s own life coincides with a desired standard level - or, put differently, the degree to which these domains satisfy individual determines his subjective well-being This ultimately define his life satisfaction. Quality of life includes everything from physical health, family, education, employment, wealth, safety, security, freedom, religious beliefs, and the environment. Other factors also include wealth, employment, physical environment, health (physical and mental), education, Leisure and Recreation time, and social belonging.

The COVID-19 situation has brought about significant changes in lives of working professionals and one of the major phenomenons of this is the mandatory work from home condition for all the working people. While working from home employees often find it challenging to maintain boundaries between work and non-work (Ramarajan & Reid, 2013). The forced confinement of workers during the COVID 19-pandemic has further complicated this issue. Job stress is considered rising and has become a challenge for the employer and because high-level stress results in low

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productivity, increased absenteeism and leads to other employees' problems like alcoholism, drug abuse, hypertension and host of cardiovascular issues (Dutta et. al., 2020). Also, that employee is the essential resource to an organization and therefore, stress depletes organizations their valued support. The Pandemic is affecting psychological as well as social well being of employees because due to lockdown real connection between people is severed and people are unable to meet their friends and sometimes even family. This is causing the feelings of apprehension, loneliness, stress and anxiety to increase which in turn might lead to poor performance at work by the employee. The new of working from home has also been a challenge to elderly employees or the ones who are not trained to handle so much technology. These people are threatened that this might cost them their jobs. Too much exposure to screen and excessive screen time is causing redness in eyes of the people and they are developing other complications as well. Lastly the threat to the employment or instability of job is what is causing maximum stress in the working professionals. There is fear in them that they might lose their jobs or might not be promoted. The wages are also not given properly. Either the employees are not given wages at all or the wages are reduced. This is affecting their financial stability and this also causing a lot of stress among the employees. This Pandemic situation has also caused problem in collaboration and hindered the team work due to inappropriate working methods. These conditions are not only impacting the social and economical domain but are also deeply affecting the psychological domain of the individual's life.

To assess the quality of life of the individual a standard questionnaire is made by the World Health Organization (WHO) which is called WHOQOL-BREF. The WHOQOL-BREF is a self-administered questionnaire comprising 26 questions on the individual's perceptions of their health and well-being over the previous two weeks, which measure the following broad domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment. Responses to questions are on a 1-5 Likert scale where 1 represents "disagree" or "not at all" and 5 represents "completely agree" or "extremely". The WHOQOL-BREF display good discriminate validity, content validity and test-retest reliability. Their sensitivity to change is currently being assessed. Domain scores produced by the WHOQOL-BREF have been shown to correlate at around 0.9 with The WHOQOL-100 domain scores.

The WHOQOL-BREF covers four domains each with specific factors. These domains are as follows:

Domain 1: Physical health

Physical health includes attributes like effectiveness in doing daily activities, dependence on medical substance or medicinal aid, energy and fatigue, mobility, pain and discomfort, sleep and rest, work capacity of an individual.

Domain 2: Psychological

Psychological factors includes satisfaction of individual with his Bodily image and appearance, Negative feelings, Positive feelings, Self-esteem, Spirituality / Religion / Personal beliefs and Thinking, learning, memory and concentration.

Domain 3: Social relationships

Social relationships domain measures satisfaction relating to Personal relationships along with Social support and Sexual activity.

Domain 4: Environment

This includes financial resources availability, Freedom, physical safety and security, Health and social care: accessibility and quality, Home environment, Opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, Participation in and opportunities for recreation / leisure activities, Physical environment (pollution / noise / traffic / climate) and Transport facility available.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- **Dr. Kaushik M., Guleria N. (2020)** conducted a research to study impact of COVID- 19 in workplace. The research paper analyzed the positive and negative aspects of work from home concept as during this COVID-19 crisis, people are compelled to live in social isolation which is also causing emotional distancing. The study has focused on the impact of COVID-19 virus pandemic on working life of employees. This research paper also emphasizes that how employers as well as HR managers are required to think out of the box and bring forth best practices as well as redefining HR roles during any adversity .This research paper also gave light on few important issues such as People-Connect , adoption of a system of Skilling, re-skilling, Up-skilling and multi-skilling people about technology, design thinking, storytelling, analytics, Artificial intelligence to prepare the workforce to become more competent and talented by enhancing their skill set.
- **Dr. Jaiswal A. & Dr. Arun J.C. (2020).** Conducted a study on Unlocking the COVID-19 lockdown: Work from home and its impact on Employees. This study was aimed at learning about the nature and quality of work in the context of the current crisis. For the study, in-depth interviews with 24 middle and senior-level managers across manufacturing and technology-enabled service sectors in India were conducted and analysis of the data was done using MAXQDA software. In the result it was evident that the employees reported an increase in working hours, major changes in their roles, reduced levels of productivity, and increased levels of stress. Besides these findings, sparks of creativity among employees during this isolation period was also discovered. These creative steps were either towards

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nurturing oneself for career growth or towards solving long-pending organizational issues. Interestingly, the creativity was self-initiated.

- **Dutta J., Mitra A., Zaman S. & Mitra A. (2020)**, conducted a study on Lockdown and Beyond: Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on global employment sector with special reference to India. In the study it was found that COVID has had a bad impact on employment conditions in India. This paper also discusses the plight of people who are not particularly working rather it discusses about 52% of rural households that earned their bread through self-employment opportunities. Casual labor accounts for 25% of rural households while regular wage earners accounted for 12.7%. The urban picture demonstrates 32.4%, 11.8% and 41.4% figures for the above three parameters. The paper also concludes that urban poverty is more dangerous than rural poverty and India's current lockdown phase combined with COVID-19 threats reclaims this fact. the worst affected sectors of global economic distress and COVID-19 impacts would include food and accommodation (144 million workers), retail and wholesale (482 million); business services and administration (157 million) and manufacturing (463 million) together adding up-to 37.5% of global employment and this is where the sharp end' of the impact of the pandemic is being felt now. These adversities have impacted the health of working professionals as well as self employed people both on physical as well as mental level.
- **International Labour Organization (ILO) Report (2020)** This report is a preliminary assessment concerning the possible impacts of COVID-19 on the world of work and proposes a range of policy options to mitigate these impacts and facilitate strong and fast recovery of economy, work culture and employees well being. According to this report the crisis has already transformed into an economic and labour market shock, impacting not only supply (production of goods and services) but also demand (consumption and investment). Prospects for the economy and the quantity and quality of employment are deteriorating rapidly. Beyond the urgent concerns about the health of workers and their families, the virus and the subsequent economic shocks will impact the world of work across three key dimensions: 1) The quantity of jobs (both unemployment and underemployment); 2) The quality of work (e.g. wages and access to social protection); and 3) Effects on specific groups who are more vulnerable to adverse labour market outcomes. Based on different scenarios for the impact of COVID-19 on global GDP growth, preliminary ILO estimates indicate a rise in global unemployment of between 5.3 million ("low" scenario) and 24.7 million ("high" scenario) from a base level of 188 million in 2019) In times of crisis, International Labour Standards provide a strong foundation for key policy responses that focus on the crucial role of decent work in achieving a sustained and equitable recovery. These standards, adopted by representatives of governments, workers' and employers' organizations, provide a human-centred approach to growth and development, including by triggering policy levers that both stimulate demand and protect workers and enterprises.
- **Walter D. (2020)**, conducted a study on implications of Covid-19 on Labor and Employment in India. In the study it was concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic has pushed the country into an unprecedented crisis and uncertainty. The research stressed on putting workers' rights and the needs, aspirations and rights of all people at the heart of economic, social and environmental policies. It was concluded that employment instability is prevalent in India which is in turn impacting the performance as well as the psychological well being of the working professionals.
- **Kniffin M.K. et. al. (2020)**, conducted a study on impact of COVID-19 at the Workplace. In the study they assessed the implications and Issues faced by the employees during the Pandemic and also suggested insights for Future Research and Action during this period. The research included study of 2 dimensions: (i) emerging changes in work practices (e.g., working from home, virtual teams) and (ii) economic and psychosocial impacts (unemployment, lockdown and loneliness, mental well-being) in light of the COVID-19 situation. In addition, they examined the potential moderating factors of age, race and ethnicity, gender, family status, personality, and cultural differences to generate disparate effects. It was concluded in the study that COVID-19 has had drastic impact on work and work culture. The new idea of working from home has challenged many employees as well as the employers in terms of lack of training and hence it has impacted the overall performance of the organization. Apart from this there is fear of losing jobs and unemployment is expected to be at rise during and after the pandemic. This is impacting the psychological aspect of employees by making them stressed and apprehensive and socially due to this instability in global economy the financial conditions are also getting affected. The COVID-19 pandemic has taken a toll on both employees and the employers; both are facing there set of challenges in adjusting to this new work culture.

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- **Hamoushe S. (2020)**, conducted a study that was aimed at examining the impact of COVID-19 outbreak on employees' mental health, specifically psychological distress and depression. The study aimed at identifying the main stressors during and after COVID-19. It also examined the main moderating factors which may mitigate or aggravate the impact of COVID-19 on employees' mental health and finally suggested recommendations from a human resource management perspective to mitigate COVID-19's impact on employees' mental health. In the result it was concluded that there is a negative impact of COVID-19 on individual's mental health. Stressors include perception of safety, threat and risk of contagion, quarantine and confinement, stigma and social exclusion as well as financial loss and job insecurity. Furthermore, three dimensions of moderating factors have been identified: organizational, institutional and individual factors. A list of recommendations was also presented to mitigate the impact of COVID-19 on the employee's mental health, during and after the outbreak, from a human resource management perspective.
- **Amit K. & Kramer Z. K. (2020)**, conducted a study to assess the potential impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on occupational status, work from home, and occupational mobility. The study concluded that the economic and social shock presented by the Covid-19 pandemic is likely to reshape perceptions of individuals and organizations about work and occupations and result in both micro and macro shifts in the world of work. In the study the focus was on three occupationally related domains that may be impacted by the pandemic. First, perceptions of the value and status of different occupations may change, resulting in both changes of occupational supply and demand (macro changes) and changes in the perceived calling and meaningfulness of different occupations (micro changes). Second, 'work from home' may change occupational perspectives on working from home. Organizations and researchers may be able to better understand which occupational and individual characteristics are associated with work-from-home effectiveness and better designate occupational groups and individuals to working (or not working) from home. Third, the increased segmentation of the labor market which allocate workers to "good jobs" and "bad jobs" and the contribution of occupational segmentation to inequality.
- **Baert S. et. al. (2020)** conducted a study to assess how the COVID-19 crisis will affect careers. For the study a survey was conducted on Belgian employees. In the result it was found that about 21% of them feared losing their jobs due to the crisis, 14% were concerned that they will even lose their jobs in the near future. In addition, 26% expected to miss out on promotions that they would have received had the COVID-19 crisis not occurred. This fear of a negative impact was higher in vulnerable groups, such migrants. It was also observed that they believed that they will look at the labor market differently and will have different work-related priorities in the future. It was also found that more than 50% of the employees indicate that they have attached more importance to working conditions and work-life balance since the COVID-19 crisis.
- **Rahman A.F.N., Ibrahim Z., Masri R. (2020)**, conducted a study describing the impact of occupational stress on employees' performances during Covid-19 pandemic. In the study to understand occupational stress on employee performance the population focusing on office hours using digital technology such as WHATSAPP and Zoom application during Covid-19 Pandemic were taken. The sample for the research comprised lecturers, senior lecturer, associate Professor and professors in a private university in Malaysia. The data was analysed using SPSS version 26 software. The key findings of this research are, the employees stress has increased due to use of excessive technology and this is also impacting their performance. Some employees are facing issues in working because they are not trained in using technology like ZOOM apps etc. Another conclusion made in the study confirmed that there is a negative correlation between occupational stress and employee commitment. The study also suggested some coping methods to deal with stress like rebalancing work and home life, taking appropriate breaks rather than having a continuous screen exposure.
- **Leitão J., Pereira D. & Gonçalves A. (2019)**, conducted a study quality of work life and its relationship with organizational performance. The study unveils the importance of subjective and behavioral components of quality of work life and their influence on the formation of the collaborator's individual desire to contribute to strengthening the organization's productivity. The results obtained indicate that for workers: feeling their supervisors' support through listening to their concerns and by sensing they take them on board; being integrated in a good work environment; and feeling respected both as professionals and as people; positively influence their feeling of contributing to organizational performance. The findings also contribute to the ongoing debate about the need for

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more work on the subjective and behavioral components of so-called smart and learning organizations, rather than focusing exclusively on remuneration as the factor stimulating organizational productivity based on the collaborator's contribution.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Purpose: To study the Quality of Life of Working Professionals during COVID-19 Pandemic.

Hypothesis: There will be a significant difference in Quality of Life among different professionals i.e. teachers, corporate professionals and doctors.

Variables: The following variables were taken for the study

Independent Variable: Professions

Dependent Variable: Quality of Life

Research Design: Quasi Experimental research design has been used for this study

Method: It is a quantitative study and data analysis is done using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SPSS. A voluntary interview was also taken to support the findings.

Sample: The sample consists of total 60 working professionals in 3 groups i.e. Group 1: Teachers, Group 2: Corporate professionals and Group 3: Doctors. Each group has 20 participants.

Tool: The tool used in the study is WHOQOL-BREF. The WHOQOL-BREF is a self-administered questionnaire comprising 26 questions on the individual's perceptions of their health and well-being over the previous two weeks, which measure the following broad domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment.

Responses to questions are on a 1-5 Likert scale where 1 represents "disagree" or "not at all" and 5 represents "completely agree" or "extremely". The WHOQOL-BREF covers four domains each with specific factors. These domains are as follows:

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Domain 2: Psychological health - Psychological factors includes satisfaction of individual with his Bodily image and appearance, Negative feelings, Positive feelings, Self-esteem, Spirituality / Religion / Personal beliefs and Thinking, learning, memory and concentration.

Domain 3: Social relationships - Social relationships domain measures satisfaction relating to Personal relationships along with Social support and Sexual activity

Domain 4: Environment - This includes financial resources availability, Freedom, physical safety and security, Health and social care: accessibility and quality, Home environment, Opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, Participation in and opportunities for recreation / leisure activities, Physical environment (pollution / noise / traffic / climate) and Transport facility available.

Reliability and Validity: The WHOQOL-BREF displays good discriminant validity, content validity and test-retest reliability. Domain scores produced by the WHOQOL-BREF have been shown to correlate at around 0.9 with The WHOQOL-100 domain scores.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data analysis was done by applying analysis of variance (ANOVA) and following results were obtained.

Table 1: This table shows the results obtained for Domain 1 i.e. Physical Domain

	P	N	Mean	SD	F	Significance
DOMAIN 1	Teachers	20	13.70	2.20	6.58	0.003
	Corporate professionals	20	13.75	3.19		
	Doctors	20	11.10	2.43		

Through table no.1 the data obtained for all the 3 groups with 20 participants each was obtained. In the result it was found that mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 13.70 and SD for this group was 2.20, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate

professionals came out to be 13.75 and SD for this group was 3.19 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 11.10 and SD for this group came out to be 2.43. F ratio came out to be 6.58.

Table 2: This table shows the results obtained for Domain 2 i.e. Mental Domain

	P	N	Mean	SD	F	Significance
DOMAIN 2	Teachers	20	12.60	2.16		

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	Corporate professionals	20	13.10	3.91	6.33	0.003
	Doctors	20	10.05	2.33		

Through table no.2 the data obtained for all the 3 groups with 20 participants each was obtained. In the result it was found that mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 12.60 and SD for this group was 2.16, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate

professionals came out to be 13.10 and SD for this group was 3.91 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 10.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.33. F ratio came out to be 6.33.

Table 3: This table shows the results obtained for Domain 3 i.e. Social Domain

	P	N	Mean	SD	F	Significance
DOMAIN 3	Teachers	20	12.95	2.68	2.26	0.114
	Corporate professionals	20	13.50	3.49		
	Doctors	20	12.05	2.46		

Through table no.3 the data obtained for all the 3 groups with 20 participants each was obtained. In the result it was found that mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 12.95 and SD for this group was 2.68, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate

professionals came out to be 13.50 and SD for this group was 3.49 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 12.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.46. F ratio came out to be 2.26.

Table 4: This table shows the results obtained for Domain 4 i.e. Environmental Domain

	P	N	Mean	SD	F	Significance
DOMAIN 4	Teachers	20	14.20	1.79	4.79	0.012
	Corporate professionals	20	13.95	2.46		
	Doctors	20	12.05	2.84		

Through table no.4 the data obtained for all the 3 groups with 20 participants each was obtained. In the result it was found that mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 14.20 and SD for this group was 1.79, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate professionals came out to be 13.95 and SD for this group was 2.46 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 12.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.84. F ratio came out to be 4.79.

mean for group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 13.70 and SD for this group was 2.20, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate professionals came out to be 13.75 and SD for this group was 3.19 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 11.10 and SD for this group came out to be 2.43. F ratio came out to be 6.58. ??There was a significant difference in quality of life in the physical parameter across the three groups. Through the voluntary interview of the participants it was found that most adversely affected group in this domain was that of the doctors. This can be attributed to the fact that doctors are the frontline workers during the pandemic hence their physical health was affected. Many reported excessive fatigue and headache while many also expressed discomfort from constantly wearing the protective PPE kits but said that they were essential for their safety. Doctors who were over 45 years of age reported pain and discomfort and also reported that excessive stress is increasing their co-morbidity of hypertension if they have it. For the other groups i.e. teachers and corporate professionals the physical domain is

DISCUSSION

This was study done with an aim to study the quality of life of working professionals during the time of COVID-19 Pandemic. The hypothesis of the study was that there will be a significant difference in quality of life across different professions i.e. teachers, corporate professionals and doctors. The tool used in the study was WHO QOL-BREF for data collection and data analysis was done using analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique. Through the result obtained it was found that in Domain 1 which is the physical health, the

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not as affected as that of doctors but people in these groups also reported physical discomforts like fatigue and redness of eyes especially related to excessive screen time due to work from home. Some reported that lack of physical activity due to lockdown has brought in lethargy in their lives but some on the contrary reported the positive side of the lockdown and said that they picked up old hobbies, some reported of practicing yoga and meditation and that has helped them keep their body and minds fit during these challenging times. In Domain 2 of mental health the mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 12.60 and SD for this group was 2.16, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate professionals came out to be 13.10 and SD for this group was 3.91 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 10.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.33. F ratio came out to be 6.33. There was a significant difference across the three groups. This domain was below average for all the groups and in this also most adversely affected were the doctors followed by the teachers and then the corporate professionals. In the telephonic interview people from all the domains reported a sense of apprehension regarding the corona virus infection. Doctors reported that since they were very close to the COVID situation some could not get enough sleep due to apprehension and stress. Other professionals reported stress due to things not being normal and some faced challenges acclimatizing to the new work from home regime. In Domain 3 of social interaction the mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 12.95 and SD for this group was 2.68, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate professionals came out to be 13.50 and SD for this group was 3.49 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 12.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.46. F ratio came out to be 2.26. Hence it was found that no significant difference existed across the groups because all the groups reported that the social interaction was curtailed due to lockdown and high communicability of the disease. Doctors reported that after work they were usually so tired that they couldn't manage time for other social interactions. This domain also was below average for all the groups because of the lockdown situation social interaction was largely curtailed. In Domain 4 of environment the mean of group 1 i.e. teachers came out to be 14.20 and SD for this group was 1.79, mean of group 2 i.e. corporate professionals came out to be 13.95 and SD for this group was 2.46 and mean of group 3 i.e. doctors came out to be 12.05 and SD for this group came out to be 2.84. F ratio came out to be 4.79. There was a significant difference across the groups as the doctors were affected more adversely here as they reported that they did not feel safe in their workplaces obviously due to the COVID-19 situation. Others also reported that going out and safety of the environment was perceived to be very low. Other aspects like sense of financial security; transportation facility etc. was reported to be average by all the groups. The overall quality of life was reported as average by teachers and corporate professionals and it was reported as below average by the doctors. This could be attributed to the fact that doctors being the frontline

workers during this pandemic were more exposed to the COVID-19 and other professions at least had a privilege to work from home and keep themselves physically safe from the virus.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Through this study it can be concluded that the COVID-19 Pandemic has created a big problem and adversity the world in terms of health care, well being as well as economy. India has also been affected adversely by this pandemic. The adverse effects are evident in health of the people; their well being is negatively affected because of this deadly virus. Apart from the health aspect, the lockdown that happened as a precautionary measure in time of the pandemic affected the economy of the nation in a negative way. The GDP of our country has dropped significantly lower which is most adversely affecting the working professionals of our country. Due to the sinking economy employment instability has increased manifold. People have either lost their jobs or are very apprehensive about the fact that they might lose their jobs in future. The currently working professionals are also not being paid full salaries; their salary is either cut to some amount or is reduced to half. These uncertainties in jobs are affecting people's financial condition. Already people are physically affected by corona conditions and psychologically also there is a lot of apprehension regarding the corona virus conditions and when will the situations be normal. All these aspects are affecting the quality of life of working professionals. Quality of life as defined by WHO is the individual's perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals. The quality of life of an individual is mainly assessed in terms of physical aspect, psychological aspect, social relationships and environmental aspect. Through various studies mentioned in the paper it can be concluded that there is negative impact of covid on quality of life of working professionals not just physically but also financially, socially and psychologically. Results of this study suggest that across professions teachers quality of life came out to be best followed by corporate professionals and then the doctors. Doctors being the front line workers were more adversely impacted during the Pandemic.

REFERENCES

- I. Baert S. et. al. (2020). How do we think COVID-19 crisis will affect our careers (if any remains)? *IZA Journal of Labour Economics*. Pg: 2 to 17
- II. Das, Dr. Kishore Kumar and Patnaik, Shalini, The Impact of COVID-19 in Indian Economy – An Empirical Study (June 26, 2020). *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, 11(3), 2020, pp. 194-202., Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3636058>
- III. Dutta J., Mitra A., Zaman S. & Mitra A. (2020). *Lockdown and Beyond: Impact of COVID-19*

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- Pandemic on global employment sector with special reference to India. *NUJS Journal of Regulatory Studies*. ISSN: 2456-4605
- IV. Hamouche S. (2020). COVID-19 and employees mental health: stressors, moderators and agenda for organizational actions. *Emerald open research journal*
 - V. International Labour Organization Report. (2020).
 - VI. Jaiswal, Akanksha & Arun, C.. (2020). Unlocking the COVID-19 Lockdown: Work from Home and Its Impact on Employees. 10.21203/rs.3.rs-34556/v1.
 - VII. Kaushik M. & Guleria N. (2020). The Impact of Pandemic COVID-19 in Workplace. *European Journal of Business and Management Vol.12*. ISSN 2222-1905.
 - VIII. Kniffin M.K. et. al. (2020). COVID-19 and the Workplace: Implications, Issues and Insights for future research and action. *Journal of Harvard Business School*.
 - IX. Pandey, Meenakshi. (2020). The Impact of Pandemic COVID -19 in Workplace. 12. 10.10.7176/EJBM/12-15-02.
 - X. Rahman A.F.N., Ibrahim Z., Masri R. (2020). Describing the impact of occupational stress on employees' performance during COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Business Society*. Pg 1-6.
 - XI. Walter D. (2020). Implications of Covid-19 for Labor and Employment in India. *The Indian Journal of Labor Economics Vol.10*. Page: 1-5.
 - XII. Leitão J., Pereira D. & Gonçalves A. (2019). Quality of Work Life and Organizational Performance: Worker's feeling of contributing, or not, to the Organization's Productivity. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health Vol. 16*. Page- 1to 18.
 - XIII. Ramarajan, L., & Reid, E. (2013). Shattering the myth of separate worlds: Negotiating non-work identities at work. *Academy of Management Review*, 38(4), 621-644.